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THE NEW VARIABLE SAMPLE SIZE SCHEMES TO MONITOR THE PROCESS MEAN OF AUTOCORRELATED TIME SERIES DATA

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Abstract: The variable sample sizes (VSS) approach to monitor the process mean of autocorrelated (within sub-group) samples using the supplementary runs-rules and synthetic schemes is proposed. To maximize the detection ability of these proposed VSS schemes, we mainly focus on the modified side-sensitive (MSS) design approach for the charting regions as it is shown that it yields the best possible performance out of all the four available design approaches. These new monitoring schemes incorporate the first-order autoregressive (i.e. AR(1)) model to the computation of the standardized charting statistics in order to account for autocorrelation. To reduce the negative effect of autocorrelation, a non-neighboring sampling method is used. Moreover, to construct dedicated Markov chain matrices, the AR(1) model and non-neighboring sampling method are incorporated into the values of probability elements to evaluate the zero- and steady-state run-length distribution. The main finding of this study is that, the proposed VSS schemes yield a uniformly better run-length performance than the existing VSS \bar{X} scheme and other Shewhart competitors. A real life example is used to illustrate the practical implementation of the proposed schemes.

Keywords: First-order autoregressive model; Markov chain; Runs-rules; Skip sampling strategy; Steady-state; Synthetic schemes; Variable sample size; Zero-state.

I. INTRODUCTION

The main tool used in statistical process monitoring (SPM) is a monitoring scheme. The most popular monitoring schemes are the Shewhart schemes, proposed by Walter A. Shewhart in the 1920's. Despite their simplicity and adaptability, the main shortcoming of Shewhart schemes is their insensitivity in detecting small to moderate size shifts. Moreover, real life properties such as autocorrelation discussed herein, as well as measurement errors discussed for instance in [1], tend to add more negative effect to the latter mentioned insensitivity in detecting small to moderate shifts. A main function of a monitoring scheme is to distinguish between chance causes of variation and assignable causes of variation. When only chance causes of variation are present, the process is said to be in-control

(IC). Otherwise, the process is said to be out-of-control (OOC) and assignable causes of variation have to be searched for and afterward removed in order to reduce or eliminate any variability in the process. A variety of enhancement / improvement approaches to increase the sensitivity of Shewhart schemes in detecting small to moderate shifts while preserving the large shifts detection ability have been discussed in the literature – to count a few: supplementary runs-rules, combining monitoring schemes with a conforming run-length (CRL) sub-scheme, variable sample size (VSS) approach, variable sampling interval (VSI) approach, variable sampling size and interval (VSSI) approach, run-sum, double sampling type schemes, etc.; in this paper, we focus only on the first three approaches.

Supplementary runs-rules have been in use since the 1950s to improve the performance of Shewhart schemes – see Koutras et al. [2]. For more recent research works on runs-rules schemes, see [3-8], etc. One other approach used to enhance the performance of the basic Shewhart scheme is to combine its operation with the CRL scheme – this yields a class of monitoring schemes called synthetic schemes, first proposed by Wu and Spedding [9] and more recently reviewed by Rakitzis et al. [10]. Monitoring schemes that incorporate a VSS approach have been generally shown in the literature to yield better OOC performance than their fixed sample size (FSS) counterparts – this was first shown in [11-13] in the case of the basic Shewhart \bar{X} to monitor the process mean of independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) observations. Later, Claro et al. [14] partly discussed the VSS \bar{X} chart for autocorrelated observations. Some other research works for VSS monitoring schemes to monitor i.i.d. observations were discussed in [15-19].

Autocorrelation within a subgroup sample is usually captured by some appropriate time series model. In this paper, we only consider the well-known first-order autoregressive model (i.e. AR(1)) as a starting point (other models will be discussed in upcoming articles). Some time series models implemented to SPM context have been reviewed by [20]. The AR(1) model is the most commonly used time series model in SPM applications due to its simplicity as compared to other stationary time series models.

The enhanced synthetic-type and 2-of-(H+1) supplementary runs-rules schemes were shown to have four categories in [10] and [21], where H is a positive integer greater than zero. These are termed non-side-sensitive (NSS), standard side-sensitive (SSS), revised side-sensitive (RSS) and modified side-sensitive (MSS) design approaches. These synthetic-type schemes denoted as IS1, IS2, IS3 and IS4 were discussed by [22], [23], [24] and [21], respectively. The improved runs-rules schemes for the NSS, SSS, RSS and MSS design approaches were discussed in [25], [26], [24] and [27] – which are denoted by IRR1, IRR2, IRR3 and IRR4, respectively. Moving forward, we denote these FSS schemes as NSS: (FSS-IS1, FSS-IRR1), SSS: (FSS-IS2, FSS-IRR2), RSS: (FSS-IS3, FSS-IRR3) and MSS: (FSS-IS4, FSS-IRR4), respectively. In contrast, when the sample size is allowed to vary, then using the categories above, the VSS schemes are denoted as NSS: (VSS-IS1, VSS-IRR1), SSS: (VSS-IS2, VSS-IRR2), RSS: (VSS-IS3, VSS-IRR3) and MSS: (VSS-IS4, VSS-IRR4), respectively. Some of the VSS research works in the latter sentence were done for i.i.d. observations; see [15] for the discussion on the VSS-IS3. Note though, no corresponding research works exist in the literature when the observations are from autocorrelated samples. The only VSS research work for autocorrelated observations using the basic \bar{X} scheme is done in Claro et al. [14].

Therefore, the main objective of this paper is to improve the basic VSS \bar{X} scheme under the effect of autocorrelation by: (i) Integrating its operation with the CRL scheme to form a synthetic \bar{X} scheme, and (ii) Adding supplementary rules to form a 2-of-(H+1) \bar{X} runs-rules schemes. Moreover,

in order to gain maximum performance from the synthetic and runs-rules schemes, we implement the MSS design – as it yields the best possible performance out of the all four existing designs. Moreover, a dedicated Markov chain matrix that is used to calculate some zero- and steady-state run-length properties of the VSS supplementary runs-rules and enhanced synthetic \bar{X} schemes. Next, the AR(1) model is used to account for autocorrelation, and to reduce the negative effect of autocorrelation, a sampling strategy that allows for skipping some successive observations (called s -skip, where s is an integer greater than 0) is incorporated in the probability values of the dedicated Markov chain matrices. The s -skip method has been shown to effectively decrease the negative effect of autocorrelation in a variety of SPM context, see for instance [28-32].

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: In Section II, the properties of VSS \bar{X} schemes with the effect of autocorrelation is discussed. The operation, construction of the Markov chain matrix and run-length properties of the proposed VSS-IS4 and VSS-IRR4 schemes are discussed in Section III. Empirical discussions of the proposed schemes, the effect of autocorrelation and comparisons with the existing FSS schemes is done in Section IV. The practical implementation of the proposed schemes is given in Section V and finally, the concluding remarks are given in Section VI.

II. VSS \bar{X} SCHEME FOR AUTOCORRELATED OBSERVATIONS USING THE SKIPPING METHOD

Assume that the quality characteristic $\{Y_{t,i}: t \geq 1; i = 1, 2, \dots, n_r\}$ is a sequence of samples ($r = 1$ (2) implies that a small (large) sample size denoted by n_1 (n_2) is used at that specific sampling point t , respectively), with $n_1 < n_2$, from an autocorrelated $N(\mu_0, \sigma_0)$ distribution that fits a stationary AR(1) model. Incorporating the s -skip method to the latter sequence still yields an AR(1) process; however, defined as $\{Y_{t,(s+1)i-s}: t \geq 1; i = 1, 2, \dots, n_r\}$ with parameter ϕ^{s+1} :

$$Y_{t,(s+1)i-s} - \mu_0 = \phi^{s+1}(Y_{t,(s+1)i-2s-1} - \mu_0) + \varepsilon'_i \quad (2)$$

with $\varepsilon'_i = \varepsilon_i + \phi\varepsilon_{i-1} + \phi^2\varepsilon_{i-2} + \dots + \phi^s\varepsilon_{i-s}$, ε_i are i.i.d. normal $(0, \sigma_\varepsilon)$ random variables; where μ_0 and σ_0 are the nominal IC mean and standard deviation process parameters, respectively, with $\sigma_0 = \frac{\sigma_\varepsilon}{\sqrt{1-\phi^2}}$, where it is assumed that $\sigma_\varepsilon = 1$ and ϕ denotes a specified parameter called a level of autocorrelation, where $|\phi| < 1$. Moreover, $Y_{t,(s+1)i-s}$ is the current observation of the time series and it depends on the previous sampled observation (after skipping s consecutive ones), i.e. $Y_{t,(s+1)i-2s-1}$; with a specified parameter ϕ (called a level of autocorrelation), where $|\phi| < 1$.

From Equation (2), we compute $\bar{Y}_t(n_r) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_r} Y_{t,(s+1)i-s} / n_r$ at sampling point t , i.e., the mean of the sample formed using the s -skip subgroup of size n_r . After the occurrence of assignable cause(s), the process mean shifts from μ_0 to $\mu_1 = \mu_0 + \delta\sigma_0$, so that $\delta = (\mu_1 - \mu_0) / \sigma_0$. Hence, the standardized statistic for each sample at the t^{th} sampling time is given by

$$Z_t(n_r) = \frac{\bar{Y}_t(n_r) - \mu_0}{\sigma_{\bar{Y}_t(n_r)}} \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{Y}_t(n_r) \sim N(\mu_1, \sigma_{\bar{Y}_t(n_r)})$, with $\sigma_{\bar{Y}_t(n_r)} = \frac{\sigma_0}{\sqrt{n_r} \rho(n_r, s, \phi)}$ and let $\rho = \rho(n_r, s, \phi)$, so that

$$\rho = \sqrt{\frac{n_r}{n_r + 2 \left(\frac{\phi^{(s+1)(n_r+1)} - n_r \phi^{2s+2} + (n_r-1)\phi^{s+1}}{(\phi^{s+1}-1)^2} \right)}} \quad (4)$$

Equation (3) is such that when $\delta = 0$, it means that the process is IC and $Z_t(n_r)$ follows an autocorrelated standard normal distribution (i.e. $Z_t(n_r) \sim N(0,1)$). However, when $\delta \neq 0$, the process is OOC and $Z_t(n_r) \sim N(\delta, 1)$.

III. RUN-LENGTH PROPERTIES OF VSS RUNS-RULES AND SYNTHETIC SCHEMES WITH S-SKIP STRATEGY

A. Operation of the VSS runs-rules and synthetic schemes

In monitoring the process mean, samples are usually taken at each sampling point to be inspected and then, each of these samples, are classified as either conforming or nonconforming depending on where the sample point plots on the charting regions shown in Figure 1; these are lower control limit (LCL), lower outer warning limit (LOWL), lower inner warning limit (LIWL), center line (CL), upper inner warning limit (UIWL), upper outer warning limit (UOWL) and upper control limit (UCL). Note that a sample plots on a conforming region when it is under the influence of common causes of variation only; however, when it plots on a nonconforming region, it implies that it has some assignable causes of variation present. In Table 1, the operational procedure of the VSS-IS4 and VSS-IRR4 schemes, where the metric, average run-length (ARL), is the average number of subgroup samples that are required before the first OOC signal is issued by a monitoring scheme and ARL_0 denotes the desired nominal ARL. Also, CRL^- (CRL^+) is number of conforming samples that fall in region E^- (E^+); which are in between the two consecutive nonconforming samples that fall on region C^- (C^+) including the nonconforming sample at the end, so that the absence of any nonconforming sample means $CRL=1$.

Table 1: Operation of the VSS-IS4 and VSS-IRR4 \bar{X} schemes with s-skip strategy

Step	VSS-IS4 / VSS-IRR4
(1)	Specify the values of H, n_1, n_2, ϕ, s and ARL_0 .
(2)	Search for k_1, k_2 and k_3 so that the attained IC ARL is equal to ARL_0 .
(3)	On the next inspection time, implement the s-skip to take a sample of size n_1 or n_2 . Calculate $Z_t(n_r)$, where $r = 2$ if $Z_{t-1}(n_r) \in \{D, D^+, D^-, B, B^+, B^-, C, C^+, C^-\}$ OR $r = 1$ if $Z_{t-1}(n_r) \in \{A, A^+, A^-\}$.
(4)	If $Z_t(n_r) \leq LCL$ or $Z_t(n_r) \geq UCL$ go to Step (8).
(5)	If $LOWL < Z_t(n_r) < UOWL$, the t^{th} sample is conforming, hence return to Step (3); otherwise go to Step (6).
(6)	If $LCL < Z_t(n_r) \leq LOWL$ go to Step (7a), or if $UOWL \leq Z_t(n_r) < UCL$ go to Step (7b).
(7)	(7a) Calculate CRL^- and if $CRL^- \leq H$ go to Step (8); otherwise return to Step (3). (7b) Compute CRL^+ and if $CRL^+ \leq H$ go to Step (8); otherwise return to Step (3).
(8)	Issue an OOC signal and then take necessary corrective action to find and remove the assignable causes. Then return to Step (3).

B. Transition probability matrix (TPM) of the VSS-IRR4 and VSS-IS4 schemes

Following a similar approach as Costa and Machado [15], this is to divide the scheme's charting region into separate distinct regions as shown in Figure 1. Let $\{Z_t(n_r); t \geq 1\}$ be a sequence of autocorrelated trials taking values in the set $\zeta_{MSS} = \{A^+, A^-, B^+, B^-, C^+, C^-, D^+, D^-\}$. Next, the probabilities of these events depend on the sample size; hence, for small sample sizes, the probability that a plotting statistic falls in the regions $A^+, A^-, B^+, B^-, C^+, C^-, D^+, D^-$ is given by $A_1^+, A_1^-, B_1^+, B_1^-, C_1^+, C_1^-, D_1^+, D_1^-$, whereas for large sample sizes, the probabilities are given by $A_2^+, A_2^-, B_2^+, B_2^-, C_2^+, C_2^-, D_2^+, D_2^-$, respectively. For some n_r , suppose that the values of μ_0 and σ_0 are known, then these probabilities are given by

$$\begin{aligned} A_r^+ &= P(CL \leq \bar{X} < UIWL) = \Phi(k_3 - \delta\sqrt{n_r}) - \Phi(-\delta\sqrt{n_r}), \\ A_r^- &= P(LIWL < \bar{X} \leq CL) = \Phi(-\delta\sqrt{n_r}) - \Phi(-k_3 - \delta\sqrt{n_r}), \\ B_r^+ &= P(UIWL \leq \bar{X} < UOWL) = \Phi(k_2 - \delta\sqrt{n_r}) - \Phi(k_3 - \delta\sqrt{n_r}), \\ B_r^- &= P(LOWL < \bar{X} \leq LIWL) = \Phi(-k_3 - \delta\sqrt{n_r}) - \Phi(-k_2 - \delta\sqrt{n_r}), \\ C_r^+ &= P(UOWL \leq \bar{X} < UCL) = \Phi(k_1 - \delta\sqrt{n_r}) - \Phi(k_2 - \delta\sqrt{n_r}), \\ C_r^- &= P(LCL < \bar{X} \leq LOWL) = \Phi(-k_2 - \delta\sqrt{n_r}) - \Phi(-k_1 - \delta\sqrt{n_r}), \\ D_r^+ &= P(\bar{X} \geq UCL) = 1 - \Phi(k_1 - \delta\sqrt{n_r}), \\ D_r^- &= P(\bar{X} \leq LCL) = \Phi(-k_1 - \delta\sqrt{n_r}), \\ A_r &= A_r^+ + A_r^-, \\ B_r &= B_r^+ + B_r^-, \\ C_r &= C_r^+ + C_r^-, \\ D_r &= D_r^+ + D_r^-. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The transition probability matrix (TPM) of the Markov chain technique for any positive integer value of $M > 0$ is given by a $(M + 1) \times (M + 1)$ matrix \mathbf{P} ,

$$\mathbf{P} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{Q} & | & \mathbf{r} \\ \hline \mathbf{0}' & | & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{Q} is the $M \times M$ essential TPM with its elements given by the probabilities in Equation (5), the $M \times 1$ vector \mathbf{r} satisfies $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{1} - \mathbf{Q}\mathbf{1}$ with the $M \times 1$ vectors given by $\mathbf{1} = (1 \ 1 \ \dots \ 1)^T$ and $\mathbf{0} = (0 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0)^T$ – see [33].

To define the run-length characteristics, we need to define the compound patterns that result in an OOC event (which is also known as the waiting time until the first occurrence of an OOC signal). For example, the sequence of plotting statistics ‘ C^+C^+ ’ indicates two consecutive plotting statistics falling in region C^+ . The symbol ‘ \pm ’ is used to denote the assumption that (at time 0) the first observation falls either in region C^+ or in region C^- , i.e. the head-start feature; so that ‘ $\pm C^-$ ’ indicate that the first plotting statistic falls either in region C^+ or C^- and the second in region C^- . Define Λ as a compound pattern if it is the union of ω distinct simple absorbing patterns i.e. $\Lambda = \Lambda_1 \cup \Lambda_2 \cup \dots \cup \Lambda_\omega$. Similarly, define Ψ as a compound pattern if it is the union of v distinct simple absorbing patterns with a head-start states i.e. $\Psi = \Psi_1 \cup \Psi_2 \cup \dots \cup \Psi_v$. Let W denote the waiting time for the first occurrence of either Λ or Ψ – as these are the absorbing states of the Markov chain.

Figure 1: The control and warning limits and the corresponding regions of the VSS-IRR4 and VSS-IS4 \bar{X} scheme

Then the run-length distribution of the improved synthetic and runs-rules \bar{X} schemes coincides with the waiting time distribution of W . Then we define the Markov chain with the state space, Ω , operating on $\{Z_t(n_r); t \geq 1\}$ as follows:

- Absorbing states (denoted by ‘OOC’) – the union of $\Lambda_1, \dots, \Lambda_\omega, \Psi_1, \dots, \Psi_v$, i.e. the $\omega+v$ states that signal the entrance of the Markov chain to an absorbing state;
- Sub-patterns (denoted by η_1, \dots, η_τ and $\psi_1, \dots, \psi_\kappa$) – the distinct first element(s) of the simple pattern $\Lambda_1, \dots, \Lambda_\omega$ and Ψ_1, \dots, Ψ_v without the last element, where $\tau < \omega$ and $\kappa < v$, respectively. For instance, if $\Lambda_1 = \{C^+B^+C^+\}$ then $\eta_1 = \{C^+B^+\}$, similarly, if $\Psi_1 = \{\pm B^+C^+\}$ then $\psi_1 = \{\pm B^+\}$;
- Central regions – two of the η_i ’s are equal to the transient states, denoted by φ_a and φ_b , corresponding

to the IC central regions for large and small samples, respectively.

For illustration purpose, we show in detail how to construct the TPMs of the VSS-IS4 and VSS-IRR4 schemes when $H = 3$. In Table 2, the compound patterns (i.e. Λ and Ψ), their corresponding sub-patterns (i.e. η and ψ) and the corresponding state spaces are shown when $H = 3$. Note that the VSS-IRR4 monitoring schemes exclude the compound (and sub-patterns) that corresponds to Ψ (and ψ), respectively. Next, we use Equations (5) to (7) to construct the corresponding TPMs shown in Table 3.

For any possible positive integer $H > 0$, the TPMs of the VSS-IS4 and VSS-IRR4 schemes are constructed in a similar fashion. That is, for other values of H , the dimension (i.e. M from Equation (6)) for the VSS-IS4 is given by $(4H)+(4H-3)$ and that of VSS-IRR4 is given by $4H$. This implies that for any $H > 0$, the dimension of the essential TPM (for each of the schemes discussed in Figure 1 and Table 1) are given by

$$M = \begin{cases} \tau & \text{for VSS-IRR4} \\ \tau + \kappa & \text{for VSS-IS4} \end{cases} \quad (7a)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \tau &= \{4H \text{ for VSS-(IRR4,IS4)} \\ \kappa &= \{4H - 3 \text{ for VSS-IS4.} \end{aligned} \quad (7b)$$

Thus, for any $H > 0$, the Ω of the VSS-IS4 and VSS-IRR4 schemes are respectively given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \{\eta_1, \dots, \eta_{\tau-1}; \eta_{\tau}^{\pm} = \varphi_a, \eta_{\tau+1}^{\pm} = \varphi_b; \eta_{\tau+2}, \dots, \eta_{\tau}; \psi_1, \dots, \psi_{\kappa}; \text{OOC}\} \\ \{\eta_1, \dots, \eta_{\tau-1}; \eta_{\tau}^{\pm} = \varphi_a, \eta_{\tau+1}^{\pm} = \varphi_b; \eta_{\tau+2}, \dots, \eta_{\tau}; \text{OOC}\}. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

That is, removing the $\psi_1, \dots, \psi_{\kappa}$ elements (corresponding to the head-start feature) on the state space of the VSS-IS4 scheme yields the state space of the VSS-IRR4 scheme.

Table 2: Components of the state space of the TPMs for the VSS-IS4 and VSS-IRR4 \bar{X} schemes when $H = 3$

Type	Λ	Ψ	φ	η	ψ	Ω
IS4	$\Lambda_1 = \{D^+\}, \Lambda_2 = \{D^-\},$ $\Lambda_3 = \{C^+C^+\},$ $\Lambda_4 = \{C^-C^-\},$ $\Lambda_5 = \{C^+B^+C^+\},$ $\Lambda_6 = \{C^+A^+C^+\},$ $\Lambda_7 = \{C^-B^-C^-\},$ $\Lambda_8 = \{C^-A^-C^-\},$ $\Lambda_9 = \{C^+E^+B^+C^+\},$ $\Lambda_{10} = \{C^+E^+A^+C^+\},$ $\Lambda_{11} = \{C^-E^-B^-C^-\},$ $\Lambda_{12} = \{C^-E^-A^-C^-\}$	$\Psi_1 = \{\pm C^+\}, \Psi_2 = \{\pm C^-\},$ $\Psi_3 = \{\pm B^+C^+\}, \Psi_4 = \{\pm A^+C^+\},$ $\Psi_5 = \{\pm B^-C^-\}, \Psi_6 = \{\pm A^-C^-\},$ $\Psi_7 = \{\pm E^+B^+C^+\},$ $\Psi_8 = \{\pm E^+A^+C^+\},$ $\Psi_9 = \{\pm E^-B^-C^-\},$ $\Psi_{10} = \{\pm E^-A^-C^-\}$	$\eta_6 = \{B^+, B^-\},$ $\eta_7 = \{A^+, A^-\}$	$\eta_1 = \{C^-E^-B^-\},$ $\eta_2 = \{C^-E^-A^-\},$ $\eta_3 = \{C^-B^-\},$ $\eta_4 = \{C^-A^-\}, \eta_5 = \{C^-\},$ $\eta_6 = \{C^+\},$ $\eta_7 = \{C^+A^+\},$ $\eta_8 = \{C^+B^+\},$ $\eta_9 = \{C^+E^+A^+\},$ $\eta_{10} = \{C^+E^+B^+\}$	$\psi_1 = \{\pm\},$ $\psi_2 = \{\pm B^+\},$ $\psi_3 = \{\pm A^+\},$ $\psi_4 = \{\pm B^-\},$ $\psi_5 = \{\pm A^-\},$ $\psi_6 = \{\pm E^+B^+\},$ $\psi_7 = \{\pm E^+A^+\},$ $\psi_8 = \{\pm E^-B^-\},$ $\psi_9 = \{\pm E^-A^-\}$	$\{\eta_1, \dots, \eta_5, \eta_6, \eta_7, \eta_8, \dots, \eta_{12}; \psi_1, \dots, \psi_9; \text{OOC}\}$
IRR4	Same as IS4	None	Same as IS4	Same as IS4	None	$\{\eta_1, \dots, \eta_5, \eta_6, \eta_7, \eta_8, \dots, \eta_{12}; \text{OOC}\}$

Table 3: TPMs of the VSS-IS4 (removing ψ_1, \dots, ψ_9 yields VSS-IRR4) schemes when $H = 3$

	η_1	η_2	η_3	η_4	η_5	η_6	η_7	η_8	η_9	η_{10}	η_{11}	η_{12}	ψ_1	ψ_2	ψ_3	ψ_4	ψ_5	ψ_6	ψ_7	ψ_8	ψ_9	OOO
η_1						$B_2^- + B_2^+$	$A_2^- + A_2^+$	C_2^+														$C_2^- + D_2^- + D_2^+$
η_2						$B_1^- + B_1^+$	$A_1^- + A_1^+$	C_1^+														$C_1^- + D_1^- + D_1^+$
η_3	B_2^-	A_2^+				B_2^+	A_2^+	C_2^+														$C_2^- + D_2^- + D_2^+$
η_4	B_1^-	A_1^+				B_1^+	A_1^+	C_1^+														$C_1^- + D_1^- + D_1^+$
η_5			B_2^-	A_2^-		B_2^+	A_2^+	C_2^+														$C_2^- + D_2^- + D_2^+$
η_6					C_2^-	$B_2^- + B_2^+$	$A_2^- + A_2^+$	C_2^+														$D_2^- + D_2^+$
η_7					C_1^-	$B_1^- + B_1^+$	$A_1^- + A_1^+$	C_1^+														$D_1^- + D_1^+$
η_8					C_2^-	B_2^-	A_2^-		A_2^+	B_2^+												$C_2^- + D_2^- + D_2^+$
η_9					C_1^-	B_1^-	A_1^-				A_1^+	B_1^+										$C_1^- + D_1^- + D_1^+$
η_{10}					C_2^-	B_2^-	A_2^-				A_2^+	B_2^+										$C_2^- + D_2^- + D_2^+$
η_{11}					C_1^-	$B_1^- + B_1^+$	$A_1^- + A_1^+$															$C_1^- + D_1^- + D_1^+$
η_{12}					C_2^-	$B_2^- + B_2^+$	$A_2^- + A_2^+$															$C_2^- + D_2^- + D_2^+$
ψ_1													B_2^+	A_2^+	B_2^-	A_2^-						$C_2^- + C_2^+ + D_2^- + D_2^+$
ψ_2					C_2^-	B_2^-	A_2^-											B_2^+	A_2^+			$C_2^- + D_2^- + D_2^+$
ψ_3					C_1^-	B_1^-	A_1^-											B_1^+	A_1^+			$C_1^- + D_1^- + D_1^+$
ψ_4						B_2^+	A_2^+	C_2^+												B_2^-	A_2^-	$C_2^- + D_2^- + D_2^+$
ψ_5						B_1^+	A_1^+	C_1^+												B_1^-	A_1^-	$C_1^- + D_1^- + D_1^+$
ψ_6					C_2^-	$B_2^- + B_2^+$	$A_2^- + A_2^+$															$C_2^- + D_2^- + D_2^+$
ψ_7					C_1^-	$B_1^- + B_1^+$	$A_1^- + A_1^+$															$C_1^- + D_1^- + D_1^+$
ψ_8						$B_2^- + B_2^+$	$A_2^- + A_2^+$	C_2^+														$C_2^- + D_2^- + D_2^+$
ψ_9						$B_1^- + B_1^+$	$A_1^- + A_1^+$	C_1^+														$C_1^- + D_1^- + D_1^+$
OOO																						1

C. Run-length properties of the VSS-IRR4 and VSS-IS4 schemes

While a number of studies tend to separately investigate zero- and steady-state run-length (RL) properties, in this paper, we consider both. The zero- and steady-state modes are used to characterize short- and long-term RL properties of a control chart, respectively. That is, a zero-state RL is a number of sampling points at which the chart first signals given it begins in some specific initial state, whereas a steady-state RL is a number of sampling points at which the chart first signals given that the process begins and stays IC for a very long time, then at some random time, an OOC signal is observed. The synthetic scheme’s head-start feature is no longer applicable in the steady-state, and thus, the head-start elements on the TPM are discarded and consequently, the VSS-IS4 scheme’s TPM is exactly the same as the VSS-IRR4 scheme’s TPM. The latter was first shown in Davis and Woodall [23] for the FSS-IS2 and FSS-IRR2. More discussions on this equivalence in the steady-state mode for other synthetic-type schemes with runs-rules schemes can be found in the Shongwe and Graham [21].

Since the TPM for any possible integer value of H has been determined, then important properties of the RL can be determined via an appropriate Markov chain technique. According to Costa and Machado [15], for VSS schemes, the first sample that is taken from the process when it is starting or after a signal is randomly decided to be small with probability p_0 , or large with probability $1 - p_0$, where $p_0 = P(LIWL < Z_t(n_r) < UIWL | LCL < Z_t(n_r) < UCL)$. (9)

So that during the IC period, the rate of inspected items per sampling (\bar{n}) is given by $\bar{n} = n_1 p_0 + n_2 (1 - p_0)$. (10)

The most used measure of a monitoring schemes’ performance is the ARL (= E(RL)), and is defined as

$$ARL = \xi^T \mathbf{R} \quad (11)$$

where ξ denotes either the $M \times 1$ zero- or steady-state initial probability vector; and \mathbf{R} is a $M \times 1$ vector

containing ARL values of being in each of the M transient states, and it is given by

$$\mathbf{R} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q})^{-1} \mathbf{1}. \quad (12)$$

Moreover, we define a vector \mathbf{N} , which is a $M \times 1$ vector containing either n_1 or n_2 , denoting a sample size vector at each of the different M transient states.

In order to compute the zero-state RL properties, then $\xi = \mathbf{q}$ of the VSS-IRR4 and VSS-IS4 schemes are respectively given by:

$$\mathbf{q}^T = (0, 0, \dots, 1 - p_0, p_0, \dots, 0, 0) \quad \text{i.e. the } \left(\frac{\tau}{2}\right)^{\text{th}} \& \left(\frac{\tau}{2} + 1\right)^{\text{th}} \text{ elements} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{q}^T = (0 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0 \ 1 \ \dots \ 0) \quad \text{i.e. the } (\tau + 1)^{\text{th}} \text{ element.}$$

Thus, the zero-state ARL (ZSARL) is computed by

$$ZSARL = \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{R} \quad (14)$$

It is essential to note that in steady-state, the VSS-IS4 scheme is equivalent to the VSS-IRR4 scheme because the head-start is no longer applicable, and hence, the elements in the TPMs are discarded in Table 2. To compute the steady-state RL properties, the non-zero initial probability vector (i.e. $\xi^T = \mathbf{u}^T$) is computed while the process is IC; that is, $A_r^+ = A_r^-$, $B_r^+ = B_r^-$, $C_r^+ = C_r^-$ and $D_r^+ = D_r^-$ as $\delta = 0$. Then using Champ [34]’s simplified cyclical steady-state method; the initial probability vector of the VSS-IRR4 and VSS-IS4 schemes is given by $\mathbf{u} = (\mathbf{1}' \mathbf{z})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{z}$, where \mathbf{z} is the $\tau \times 1$ vector given by $\mathbf{z} = (\mathbf{G} - \mathbf{Q}')^{-1} \mathbf{q}$, with the $\tau \times \tau$ matrix \mathbf{G} , given by $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{q} \cdot \mathbf{1}' + \mathbf{I}$, where \mathbf{q} corresponds to that of the VSS-IRR4 schemes’ in Equation (13).

Thus, the steady-state ARL (SSARL) is computed by

$$SSARL = \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{R}. \quad (15)$$

In addition to Equations (14) and (15), a number of researchers in the SPM literature have advocated for the use of average number of samples (ANOS) to evaluate the performance of VSS schemes, and these are given by

$$\mathbf{q}^T (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q})^{-1} \mathbf{N} \text{ and } \mathbf{u}^T (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{Q})^{-1} \mathbf{N} \quad (16)$$

in zero- and steady-state mode, respectively.

To evaluate the performance of the proposed schemes from an overall performance perspective, the expected *ARL* (*EARL*) and the expected *ANOS* (*EANOS*) are used because users tend not to know beforehand what exact shift value(s) is targeted – see for example, Wu et al. [35] and You [36]. The *EARL* and *EANOS* measure the performance of a monitoring scheme over a range of shift values, i.e. δ_{\min} to δ_{\max} – which are the lower and the upper bound of δ , respectively. Note that the shifts within the interval $[\delta_{\min}, \delta_{\max}]$ usually occur according to a pdf equal to $f(\delta)$ which is usually unknown. In the absence of any particular information, it is usually assumed that the shifts in the process mean happen with an equal probability, then $f(\delta) = 1/(\delta_{\max} - \delta_{\min})$ i.e. a uniform $U(\delta_{\min}, \delta_{\max})$ distribution. The proposed schemes are designed in such a manner that at each desired H value, we fix k_1 and k_3 , then implement a search algorithm for a value of k_2 so that the attained IC *ARL* is equal to the target ARL_0 , and then at each different H value, we choose the combination of design parameters that yield the best overall performance for a range of specified shifts and it is achieved by using

$$(H, k_1, k_2^*, k_3) = \underset{(H, k_1, k_2, k_3)}{\operatorname{argmin}} EARL$$

subject to

$$ARL(\delta = 0) = ARL_0 \tag{17}$$

with

$$EARL = \int_{\delta_{\min}}^{\delta_{\max}} ARL(\delta) f(\delta) d\delta$$

with $\delta \in [\delta_{\min}, \delta_{\max}]$. That is, to choose the parameters that yield the smallest *EARL*, where $ARL(\delta)$ is the *ARL* as a function of the shift δ in the parameter under surveillance. Note that equivalently using the *EANOS* which is given by

$$EANOS = \int_{\delta_{\min}}^{\delta_{\max}} ANOS(\delta) f(\delta) d\delta \tag{18}$$

yields the same optimal design parameters, where $ANOS(\delta)$ is the *ANOS* as a function of δ in the parameter under surveillance, with the nominal *ANOS* denoted by $ANOS_0$ (calculated as $ANOS_0 = \bar{n} \times ARL_0$). Since $f(\delta)$ has a Uniform distribution, we may equivalently write the expressions of the *EARL* and *EANOS* as,

$$EARL = \frac{1}{\Delta} \sum_{\delta=\delta_{\min}}^{\delta_{\max}} ARL(\delta) \tag{19}$$

$$EANOS = \frac{1}{\Delta} \sum_{\delta=\delta_{\min}}^{\delta_{\max}} ANOS(\delta) \tag{20}$$

respectively; where Δ is the number of increments from δ_{\min} to δ_{\max} .

IV. EMPIRICAL DISCUSSION

A. IC design parameters

For illustration purpose, consider Table 4 where $k_1 \in \{3.1, 3.5\}$ and $k_3=0.6745$, separately, in the zero- and steady-states, as H increases, the values of k_2 such that the attained IC *ARL* is equal to ARL_0 converge to some specific value no matter how large H gets (see boldfaced values in

Table 4). A similar pattern is observed for other values of ARL_0 .

Table 4: The values of k_2 for the zero- and steady-state VSS-IRR4 and VSS-IS4 schemes when $k_1 \in \{3.1, 3.5\}$, $H \in \{1, 2, \dots, 20\}$, $ARL_0=370.4$ and $k_3=0.6745$

H	$k_1=3.1$			$k_1=3.5$		
	ZS	ZS	SS	ZS	ZS	SS
	IRR4	IS4	IRR4 & IS4	IRR4	IS4	IRR4 & IS4
1	2.0393	2.0664	2.0398	1.8221	1.8401	1.8227
2	2.1150	2.1469	2.1157	1.9056	1.9269	1.9064
3	2.1425	2.1765	2.1433	1.9357	1.9585	1.9366
4	2.1544	2.1894	2.1553	1.9486	1.9721	1.9496
5	2.1600	2.1954	2.1609	1.9545	1.9782	1.9555
6	2.1626	2.1982	2.1635	1.9572	1.9811	1.9583
7	2.1638	2.1996	2.1648	1.9585	1.9825	1.9596
8	2.1644	2.2002	2.1654	1.9591	1.9832	1.9602
9	2.1647	2.2006	2.1657	1.9594	1.9835	1.9605
10	2.1649	2.2007	2.1659	1.9595	1.9836	1.9606
11	2.1649	2.2008	2.1659	1.9596	1.9837	1.9607
12	2.1650	2.2008	2.1660	1.9597	1.9837	1.9608
13	2.1650	2.2009	2.1660	1.9597	1.9837	1.9608
14	2.1650	2.2009	2.1660	1.9597	1.9837	1.9608
15	2.1650	2.2009	2.1660	1.9597	1.9837	1.9608
16	2.1650	2.2009	2.1660	1.9597	1.9837	1.9608
17	2.1650	2.2009	2.1660	1.9597	1.9837	1.9608
18	2.1650	2.2009	2.1660	1.9597	1.9837	1.9608
19	2.1650	2.2009	2.1660	1.9597	1.9837	1.9608
20	2.1650	2.2009	2.1660	1.9597	1.9837	1.9608

B. Comparison of the effect of autocorrelation on the VSS-IRR4 and VSS-IS4 schemes

In Tables 5 and 6, we discuss the zero- and steady-state OOC performance of the basic \bar{X} , IRR4 and IS4 schemes under the i.i.d. case (i.e. $\phi=0$, no autocorrelation) and autocorrelated case (i.e. $\phi=0.5$) using the (*ARL&EARL*) and (*ANOS&EANOS*), respectively. For ease in comparison, we define the following percentage difference (%Diff) metrics,

$$\%Diff1 = \frac{EARL_{FSS} - EARL_{VSS}}{EARL_{VSS}} \times 100\%$$

where $EARL_{FSS}$ ($EARL_{VSS}$) is the *EARL* of the corresponding FSS (VSS) scheme, respectively; however,

$$\%Diff2 = \frac{EARL_{\phi=0} - EARL_{\phi=0.5}}{EARL_{\phi=0.5}} \times 100\%$$

where $EARL_{\phi}$ is the *EARL* at some specific value of ϕ ; and finally,

$$\%Diff3 = \frac{EANOS_{\phi=0} - EANOS_{\phi=0.5}}{EANOS_{\phi=0.5}} \times 100\%$$

where $EANOS_{\phi}$ is the *EANOS* at some specific value of ϕ .

Firstly, in Table 5, it is observed that for i.i.d. case, the VSS-IS4 scheme has a uniformly better OOC *ZSARL* than its FSS counterpart; however, the VSS-IRR4 and VSS- \bar{X} schemes only have a better *ZSARL* than its FSS counterparts for small to moderate shifts. With respect to the *SSARL*, the VSS schemes outperform their FSS schemes for small to moderate shifts only. However, for the autocorrelated case, the VSS schemes are uniformly better than its FSS counterparts for all shift values. Secondly, based on the overall performance, the *EARLs* of VSS scheme are always smaller than those of the FSS counterparts for both i.i.d. and autocorrelated cases. The latter is illustrated by the values of %Diff1 on Table 5 that

are always greater than zero. Note though, this difference is more pronounced in the i.i.d. case than in the autocorrelated case. Thirdly, increasing ϕ causes a negative effect on the performance of a monitoring scheme for both the FSS and VSS schemes. For example, increasing ϕ from 0 to 0.5 causes the ZSARL to increase from 135.8 to 184.0 when $\delta=0.25$ for the VSS-IS4; overall, using Equation (19), it follows that zero-state EARL increases from 43.1 to 50.5 (i.e. based on a %Diff2, it yields a 14.6% deterioration).

Note that the FSS-IRR4 and FSS-IS4 schemes discussed in this section are not yet available in the SPM literature and these are the improved versions of the basic MSS run-rules and synthetic schemes for autocorrelated observations proposed in Shongwe et al. [32]. Since it is shown in Tables 5 that the corresponding VSS-IRR4 and VSS-IS4 schemes tends to have a better detection ability than the

FSS-IRR4 and FSS-IS4 schemes for the same \bar{n} , we opted to only focus on the VSS schemes hereafter.

Similarly, in Table 6, at each corresponding values of δ , the zero- and steady-state ANOS (denoted by ZSANOS and SSANOS, respectively) increase when ϕ is increased from 0 to 0.5, indicating a deterioration in performance for different \bar{n} values. This is illustrated by the fact that the EANOS at $\phi=0.5$ are always higher than those at $\phi=0$, and thus each corresponding %Diff3 indicates a deterioration at different \bar{n} values.

From Tables 5 and 6, it is observed that the corresponding zero- and steady-state RL properties (i.e. ZSARL and SSARL, as well as ZSANOS and SSANOS) of the VSS-IRR4 scheme at each shift values are very close to each other – see the summary in Remark 1. Consequently, in an effort to preserve space, only the steady-state RL properties are shown for the VSS-IRR4 scheme hereafter.

Table 5: The zero- and steady-state ARL and EARL of the (FSS and VSS) IRR4 and IS4 schemes when $\phi \in \{0,0.5\}$, $s=0$, $n_1=1$, $n_2=3$, $\bar{n}=2$, $H=3$, $\delta_{min}=0$, $\delta_{max}=3$ and $ARL_0=370.4$

ϕ	δ	\bar{X}		Zero-state				Steady-state	
		FSS	VSS	IRR4		IS4		IRR4&IS4	
				FSS	VSS	FSS	VSS	FSS	VSS
0	0	370.4	370.4	370.4	370.4	370.4	370.4	370.4	370.4
	0.25	223.9	220.4	154.1	142.8	148.1	135.8	153.9	142.6
	0.5	90.7	80.5	45.3	37.8	39.4	31.4	45.1	37.6
	0.75	38.1	28.9	17.1	13.2	13.0	9.1	17.0	13.1
	1	17.7	11.8	8.3	6.3	5.5	3.6	8.2	6.2
	1.25	9.2	5.8	4.9	3.9	3.0	2.0	4.8	3.8
	1.5	5.3	3.5	3.4	2.8	1.9	1.4	3.3	2.8
	1.75	3.3	2.4	2.6	2.3	1.5	1.2	2.5	2.2
	2	2.3	1.9	2.1	2.0	1.3	1.1	2.1	1.9
	2.25	1.8	1.6	1.8	1.7	1.1	1.0	1.7	1.7
	2.5	1.4	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.1	1.0	1.5	1.6
	2.75	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.0	1.0	1.4	1.5
	3	1.1	1.3	1.2	1.4	1.0	1.0	1.2	1.4
	EARL	59.0	56.2	47.2	45.2	45.3	43.1	47.2	45.1
	%Diff1	4.8%		4.5%		5.1%		4.5%	
0.5	0	370.4	370.4	370.4	370.4	370.4	370.4	370.4	370.4
	0.25	259.5	259.6	194.5	189.6	189.3	184.0	194.3	189.5
	0.5	126.9	124.5	69.3	65.1	62.9	58.4	69.1	64.9
	0.75	60.7	56.8	28.3	25.7	23.2	20.4	28.1	25.5
	1	30.8	27.1	13.8	12.2	10.1	8.5	13.7	12.1
	1.25	16.7	14.0	7.9	6.9	5.2	4.3	7.8	6.8
	1.5	9.8	7.9	5.1	4.5	3.1	2.6	5.1	4.5
	1.75	6.1	4.9	3.7	3.3	2.2	1.8	3.6	3.3
	2	4.1	3.4	2.9	2.7	1.7	1.4	2.8	2.6
	2.25	2.9	2.5	2.4	2.2	1.4	1.2	2.3	2.2
	2.5	2.2	2.0	2.0	2.0	1.2	1.1	2.0	1.9
	2.75	1.8	1.7	1.8	1.7	1.1	1.1	1.8	1.7
	3	1.5	1.4	1.6	1.6	1.1	1.0	1.6	1.6
	EARL	68.7	67.4	54.1	52.9	51.8	50.5	54.0	52.8
	%Diff1	2.0%		2.3%		2.6%		2.3%	
	%Diff2	-14.1%	-16.6%	-12.8%	-14.6%	-12.5%	-14.6%	-12.7%	-14.7%

Table 6: The zero-state (ZS) and steady-state (SS) ANOS and EANOS of the basic \bar{X} , VSS-IRR4 and VSS-IS4 schemes when $\phi \in \{0,0.5\}$, $s=0$, $n_1=1$, $n_2=3, \bar{n} \in \{2,4\}$, $H=3$, $\delta_{min}=0$, $\delta_{max}=3$ and $ANOS_0 \in \{740.8, 1481.6\}$

	\bar{n}	2								4							
		Mode		SS		ZS		ZS		Xbar		SS		ZS		ZS	
		Scheme	Xbar	IRR4&IS4	IRR4	IS4	IRR4	IS4	IRR4	IS4	Xbar	IRR4&IS4	IRR4	IS4	IRR4	IS4	IRR4
ϕ	0	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	0	0.5	
δ	0	740.8	740.8	740.8	740.8	740.8	740.8	740.8	740.8	1481.6	1481.6	1481.6	1481.6	1481.6	1481.6	1481.6	1481.6
	0.25	451.5	527.3	291.7	384.5	292.1	384.9	278.8	374.4	621.5	919.4	335.5	608.1	336.5	609.0	307.5	584.2
	0.5	176.5	264.8	81.8	137.5	82.3	138.0	69.4	124.6	161.0	380.3	70.9	179.5	71.5	180.4	52.7	155.0
	0.75	68.9	128.7	30.6	57.2	30.9	57.6	22.1	46.7	50.5	159.1	26.8	69.2	27.1	69.8	16.5	51.9
	1	30.2	65.6	15.3	28.6	15.5	28.9	9.7	20.9	21.3	72.9	15.3	34.6	15.5	35.0	9.0	22.9
	1.25	15.3	35.7	9.5	16.9	9.7	17.1	5.7	11.2	11.9	37.5	10.9	21.2	11.1	21.5	7.0	13.1
	1.5	9.0	20.8	6.9	11.3	7.1	11.5	4.1	7.1	8.3	21.7	8.7	15.0	8.8	15.3	6.3	9.2
	1.75	6.1	13.1	5.5	8.3	5.6	8.5	3.5	5.2	6.7	14.1	7.3	11.7	7.4	11.9	6.1	7.5
	2	4.6	8.8	4.7	6.6	4.7	6.7	3.2	4.2	5.8	10.1	6.5	9.7	6.5	9.9	6.0	6.7
	2.25	3.8	6.4	4.1	5.5	4.1	5.6	3.1	3.7	5.3	7.8	5.9	8.3	6.0	8.4	6.0	6.3
	2.5	3.3	4.9	3.6	4.7	3.7	4.8	3.0	3.4	4.9	6.5	5.4	7.3	5.5	7.3	6.0	6.1
	2.75	3.0	3.9	3.3	4.1	3.4	4.2	3.0	3.2	4.6	5.7	5.0	6.4	5.1	6.5	6.0	6.0
	3	2.8	3.3	3.1	3.7	3.1	3.7	3.0	3.1	4.3	5.1	4.7	5.8	4.7	5.9	6.0	6.0
EANOS	116.6	140.3	92.4	108.4	92.5	108.6	88.4	103.7	183.7	240.1	152.7	189.1	152.9	189.4	147.4	181.3	
%Diff3		-16.9%		-14.8%		-14.8%		-14.8%		-23.5%		-19.3%		-19.3%		-18.7%	

Remark 1: Let the zero- & steady-state EARL and EANOS be denoted by ZSEARL, SSEARL, ZSANOS and SSEANOS; respectively. Then the percentage difference for the VSS-IRR4 scheme (i.e. $\frac{ZSEARL - SSEARL}{SSEARL} \times 100\%$ and $\frac{ZSEANOS - SSEANOS}{SSEANOS} \times 100\%$) are always less than 1%.

C. The VSS-IRR4 and VSS-IS4 schemes with s-skip sampling strategy

In Tables 7 and 8, the effect of using s-skip strategy (with s=3) instead of the no-skip strategy is studied for the VSS-IS4 scheme in terms of the steady-state EARL and EANOS, respectively. The OOC performance illustration is shown for $H \in \{1,2,\dots,12\}$ as per illustration in Table 4 to observe what happens to the EARL and EANOS as k_2 approaches the convergence property shown therein for $k_1=3.5$.

To investigate what value of H has the optimal overall performance gain (OPG) such that increasing H does not yield any further significant OPG. To do so, two metrics are defined as follows,

$$\%Diff4 = \frac{EARL_{s=0} - EARL_{s=3}}{EARL_{s=3}}$$

for a given value of H; however, for a specific value of s,

$$OPG(H) = \frac{EARL_{H-1} - EARL_H}{EARL_H} \tag{21}$$

where $EARL_{s=0}$ and $EARL_H$ denote the EARL of the s=0 sampling strategy (with H fixed) and at a specific value of H (with s fixed), respectively – the others are defined in a similar manner. Similarly, %Diff4 and OPG(H) is defined in a similar manner with EARL replaced by EANOS for Table 8 purpose.

Table 7: The steady-state EARL of the VSS-IS4 and VSS-IRR4 schemes with $s = 0 \& 3$, and $H \in \{1,2,\dots,12\}$, %Diff4 and the OPG(H) in brackets when $\phi=0.75$, $n_1=1$, $n_2=3$ and $\bar{n}=2$

H	$EARL_{s=0}$	$EARL_{s=3}$	%Diff4
1	60.4	52.8	14.4%
2	57.9 (4.3%)	51.1 (3.3%)	13.4%
3	56.5 (2.5%)	50.0 (2.1%)	12.9%
4	55.6 (1.6%)	49.4 (1.3%)	12.6%
5	55.0 (1.0%)	49.0 (0.9%)	12.4%
6	54.7 (0.6%)	48.7 (0.5%)	12.3%
7	54.5 (0.4%)	48.5 (0.4%)	12.3%
8	54.3 (0.3%)	48.4 (0.2%)	12.2%
9	54.2 (0.2%)	48.3 (0.1%)	12.2%
10	54.2 (0.1%)	48.3 (0.1%)	12.2%
11	54.1 (0.1%)	48.3 (0.0%)	12.2%
12	54.1 (0.0%)	48.3 (0.0%)	12.2%

Table 8: The steady-state EANOS of the VSS-IS4 and VSS-IRR4 schemes with $s = 0 \& 3$, and $H \in \{1,2,\dots,12\}$, %Diff4 and the OPG(H) in brackets when $\phi=0.75$, $n_1=1$, $n_2=3$ and $\bar{n}=2$

H	$EANOS_{s=0}$	$EANOS_{s=3}$	%Diff4
1	124.4	108.4	14.8%
2	119.0 (4.3%)	104.7 (3.3%)	13.6%
3	116.0 (2.5%)	102.5 (2.1%)	13.1%
4	114.1 (1.6%)	101.1 (1.3%)	12.8%
5	112.9 (1.0%)	100.2 (0.9%)	12.6%
6	112.1 (0.6%)	99.6 (0.5%)	12.5%
7	111.6 (0.4%)	99.3 (0.4%)	12.4%
8	111.3 (0.3%)	99.0 (0.2%)	12.4%
9	111.1 (0.2%)	98.9 (0.1%)	12.4%
10	111.0 (0.1%)	98.8 (0.1%)	12.4%
11	110.9 (0.1%)	98.7 (0.0%)	12.3%
12	110.9 (0.0%)	98.7 (0.0%)	12.3%

In Tables 7 and 8, it is observed that increasing s from the 0-skip strategy to 3-skip strategy yields a performance gain of at least 12% in EARL and EANOS, for all considered values of H. For example, when H=1, the percentage gains of using the 3-skip strategy instead of the 0-skip strategy are 14.4% and 14.8% in terms of EARL and EANOS, respectively. Next, the EARL's OPG of using H=2 instead of H=1 when 0-skip and 3-skip sampling strategies are implemented are 4.3% and 3.3% (see Table 7), respectively. Moreover, in Tables 7 and 8, it is observed that when H>5, the OPGs of both the 0-skip and 3-skip

strategies are all less than 1% indicating that increasing H greater than 5 do not yield any more significant percentage gains. More importantly, it is observed that as H approaches the values of H where k_2 starts to converge (see Table 4 for the convergence property, i.e. around H equal to 11) the OPG approaches a percentage value of 0 – indicating that there is no benefit in overall performance, at all, by continually increasing the value of H for the VSS-IS4 s -skip scheme in zero-state beyond the converged values of k_2 by using either the $EARL$ or $EANOS$.

V. IMPLEMENTATION EXAMPLE

Consider the data for the weight of yogurt cup filling process taken from page 670 of Costa and Castagliola [28]. For the sake of illustration purpose here, assume there are no measurement errors and that this is a full dataset. That is, the dataset has 20 samples corresponding to a 20-hours sequence of production. The Phase I analysis of this process indicated that the weight of a yogurt cup, $Y_{t,(s+1)i-s}$, fits an AR(1) model with parameter $\phi = 0.38$, an IC mean estimate, $\mu_0 = 124.9g$ and an IC standard deviation, $\sigma_0 = 0.76g$. We intend to show how to implement the s -skip sampling strategy for $s=1$ and form rational subgroups of size $n_1=2$ and $n_2=4$.

Using Equations (3) and (4), the relevant parameters are calculated as follows:
 $\rho(n_1, 1, 0.38)=0.9348$, $\sigma_{\bar{Y}_t(n_1)}=0.5749$, $\rho(n_2, 1, 0.38)=0.8984$, $\sigma_{\bar{Y}_t(n_2)}=0.4230$.

Assume that $H=3$, then from Table 4, it follows that when we take the standardized limits as $k_1=3.5$ and $k_3=0.6745$, then the corresponding $k_2=1.9366$. That is, the charting region is divided as follow: $D^- \in (-\infty, -3.5]$, $C^- \in (-3.5, -1.9366]$, $B^- \in (-1.9366, -0.6745]$, $A^- \in (-0.6745, 0]$, $A^+ \in [0, 0.6745]$, $B^+ \in [0.6745, 1.9366]$, $C^+ \in [1.9366, 3.5]$, $D^+ \in [3.5, \infty)$.

Next, Table 9 is constructed to show the relevant charting statistic values when $s = 1$. For example, the charting statistics of the sampling point $t = 1$ and 2, are calculated as follows when $s = 1$:

- At $t = 1$, the sampling size equal to n_1 is used because a process is assumed to have been IC for a long time. Hence, $\bar{Y}_1(n_1) = \frac{1}{n_1}(Y_{1,1} + Y_{1,3}) = 125.40$ & $Z_1(n_1) = \frac{\bar{Y}_1(n_1) - \mu_0}{\sigma_{\bar{Y}_t(n_1)}} = \frac{125.40 - 124.9}{0.5749} = 0.87$, falling in region B^+ .
- At $t = 2$, the sampling size equal to n_2 is used because the $Z_1(n_r)$ plotted in region B^+ - see Step (3) in Table 1. Hence, $\bar{Y}_2(n_2) = \frac{1}{n_2}(Y_{2,1} + Y_{2,3} + Y_{2,5} + Y_{2,7}) = 124.93$ & $Z_2(n_2) = \frac{\bar{Y}_2(n_2) - \mu_0}{\sigma_{\bar{Y}_t(n_2)}} = 0.06$, falling in region A^+ .

Since at $t=2$, the charting statistic plotted in region A^+ , then according to Step (3) of Table 1, at sampling point $t=3$, the sample size equals n_1 ; and so on.

Based on the analysis in Table 9, it is observed that the VSS-IRR4 and VSS-IS4 \bar{X} schemes yields the first OOC signal at sampling point 12 when s is equal to 0 and 1 – see Steps 6 and 7(b) in Table 1; indicative of a downwards shift in the process mean. Thus, it follows that the weight of the yogurt cups were observed, from sampling point 12, to

have a significant downwards shift from the desired IC value of approximately 124.9g, due to some undesired assignable cause(s). After investigation, it was observed that it was due to a clog in the machine.

Table 9: The sample size and charting statistic at each sampling point and classification on the charting region of the VSS-IRR4 and VSS-IS4 scheme

t	n_r	$\bar{Y}_t(n_r)$	$Z_t(n_r)$	Region	Signal
1	n_1	125.40	0.87	B^+	No
2	n_2	124.93	0.06	A^+	No
3	n_1	125.15	0.43	A^+	No
4	n_1	125.35	0.78	B^+	No
5	n_2	124.65	-0.59	A^-	No
6	n_1	125.25	0.61	A^+	No
7	n_1	125.00	0.17	A^+	No
8	n_1	124.35	-0.96	B^-	No
9	n_2	125.38	1.12	B^+	No
10	n_2	125.10	0.47	A^+	No
11	n_1	123.55	-2.35	C^-	No
12	n_2	123.65	-2.96	C^-	Yes
13	n_2	123.48	-3.37	C^-	No
14	n_2	123.15	-4.14	D^-	Yes
15	n_2	123.63	-3.01	C^-	No
16	n_2	123.53	-3.25	C^-	Yes
17	n_2	123.63	-3.01	C^-	No
18	n_2	123.23	-3.96	D^-	Yes
19	n_2	123.40	-3.55	D^-	Yes
20	n_2	123.53	-3.25	C^-	No

VI. CONCLUSION

The VSS synthetic and 2-of- $(H+1)$ runs-rules schemes are proposed using the MSS design for the charting regions when the process mean observations are under the effect autocorrelation. The s -skip strategy is used to reduce the negative effect of autocorrelation (with autocorrelation modelled by an AR (1) process). While the VSS synthetic scheme is shown to have a uniformly better OOC performance than its considered competitors in zero- and steady-state; the VSS runs-rules scheme has a good performance for small-to-moderate shift values. Using overall performance measures (i.e. the $EARL$ or $EANOS$ metrics), both the VSS synthetic and runs-rules schemes (with s -skip strategy) always yield a better zero- and steady-state performance than the considered competitors in all the corresponding cases. More importantly, values of $H > 5$ are not recommended. A drawback of these new schemes is that, they require more observations (as some will be skipped during inspection) as compared standard monitoring schemes.

For future research, the VSS synthetic and runs-rules schemes need to be extended: (i) to account for parameter estimation effect (see for instance Garza-Venegas et al. [37]); (ii) to use the new combined mixed samples & s -skip strategy (discussed in Shongwe et al. [38]); (iii) to instead vary both the sample sizes and sampling intervals when the process mean is under the combined effect of autocorrelation and measurement errors.

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